

Operationalising Open schooling on Scale for Science and Sustainability Curricula: The case of Greece

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Abstract. Open schooling is a term promoted by the European Union that refers to schools as agents of community wellbeing. However limited attention has been paid to examining how to adopt and scale up open schooling to make it sustainable. In this study, we present our way to operationalise open schooling on a large scale by creating agile, written by teachers, led by theory, coached by experts, curriculum resources that exploit the existing curriculum and school context (bottom-up approach). It was a 3-year effort in the context of the CONNECT project implemented in Greece where more than 142 schools, 340 teachers and 5390 students implemented open schooling for Science and Sustainability curriculum in each kind of school. First, we present the principles and the guidelines set, in order to create the open schooling educational resources. Then, we present the educational scenarios written by the teachers and how they were implemented. Then, we present some results from a questionnaire that is given to students for us to understand what kind of activities took place in this large scale open schooling implementation, what was the students' school level and the level of students' acceptance of the program. We finally discuss and conclude focusing on emerging insights on how to scale up open schooling and make it sustainable in existing school settings with implications on local, regional, national and global educational policy.

1. Introduction

Open schooling is a term promoted by the European Union [1] that refers to schools as agents of community wellbeing. As Okada & Gray [2] underlines, the European Union has funded more than 15 projects on open schooling to enhance science education towards sustainability in Europe. However as the same authors claim "limited attention has been paid to examining how to adopt and scale up these initiatives to make them sustainable".

Okada & Gray [2] and Mulero, Cunill, Grau & Mancho [3] also claim that most of the times open schooling implementation contradicts traditional curricula. Okada et al. [4] found that this is the case mostly on educational systems where the curriculum is focused on exams. Mulero et al. [3] conclude in their work that the main obstacles for implementing open schooling in schools are (a) the division of the curriculum by subjects, each with their own structure and contents, whereas in real life issues are not divided into subjects, (b) in secondary education, the strict, traditional confines of different classes which prevents addressing issues in a more realistic overarching way and finally the (c) lack of available time to line up course contents.

In this paper, we present our way to operationalise open schooling on a large scale by creating agile, written by teachers, led by theory, coached by experts, resources that exploit the existing curriculum and school context. It was a 3-year effort in the context of the CONNECT project implemented in Greece where more than 142 schools, 340 teachers and 5390 students implemented open schooling for Science and Sustainability curriculum in 12 out of 13 regions of Greece in each kind of school (Primary education, Secondary education, Special Educational Needs Schools, General schools, Vocational schools, very small schools in a small island or high on the mountains, big urban schools).

The aim is to discuss a set of principles that could assist teachers and policy makers in creating and implementing open schooling curriculum resources that fit the school context using mostly a bottom-up approach.

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2. Operationalising open schooling by writing and implementing theory-based open schooling resources

2.1. Educational resources design principles and guidelines

Following theory and practice on open schooling [1-2, 4, 5-8] in the context of the CONNECT project (<https://www.connect-science.net/>) we created a set of guidelines for authoring and implementing an educational scenario for operationalising the theory of open schooling in context but also in scale. The principles and guidelines are presented below:

1. Students and teacher have to study a real problem or challenge, global or local, that can be studied using Science or STEAM
2. The educational scenario is connected to the curriculum or can be implemented in extra-curricular activities in the school context (environmental school activities, science clubs etc.)
3. The educational scenario follows the model Care-Know-Do [2]
4. Students and teacher are supported by an expert on the field of the problem/challenge and are also encouraged
5. to engage other stakeholders of the community (decision makers, research centers, universities, museums, NGO's, industry) in any phase of the Care-Know-Do model is appropriate
6. The educational scenario involves the family of the students in any phase of the Care-Know-Do model is appropriate
7. The educational scenario aims at least one of the 17 goals of sustainable development of the United Nations.

2.2. The educational scenarios written and implemented by teachers

Teachers had initially access to 5 educational scenarios written by CONNECT's expert teams two (2) structured ("Rewilding", "Carbon Neutral") plus three (3) open ended scenarios ("jury", "consensus", "co-creation") but in order to scale up and sustain open schooling, teachers were given the opportunity to write their own scenarios or translate and customize other CONNECT scenarios written in English that fit in their needs. Finally they chose two (2) more scenarios: "Microplastics" by MasteryScience and "How does hand washing relate to the risk of contamination?" by IRSI.

Following the above mentioned design principles and guidelines and coached by curriculum experts of Regional Directorate of P&S Education of Crete (RDE), some teachers have written educational scenarios-science actions which they shared with the others teachers through the CONNECT platform

(<https://connect-eu.exus.co.uk/>) [9]. Twenty-One (21) educational scenarios were written by teachers and approved by RDE experts and uploaded in the CONNECT platform and twenty (20) of them were implemented in schools. Three (3) more implemented scenarios have not been uploaded yet. In total, $20+5+2+3=30$ educational scenarios were implemented throughout these three (3) years. You can see below the 20 educational scenarios written by teachers and uploaded on the platform and how they were implemented in Greek schools (Table 1).

Table 1. The educational scenarios written by teachers

Name	Curriculum according the description of the scenario	School level	Curriculum according on how it were implemented in practice	Teachers involved in implementation
Renewable energy sources	Physics and Geography	Lower Secondary Education	Physics	Individual
Polymer plastics	Chemistry	Upper Secondary Education (11th Grade)	Chemistry	Individual
Creating & Using maps for Problem Solving	Geography	Lower Secondary Education (7th Grade)	Geography	Individual
Plastics and Food	Chemistry	Upper Secondary Education	Chemistry. with additional activities following the students' interests and current affairs	Individual
Aerosols in Virus Transmission	Chemistry-Biology-Mathematics-Computer Science	Secondary Education	“School activities” (environmental, health education, school and professional orientation, cultural) Interdisciplinary and interdisciplinary way.	Group of teachers
Wildlife in Greece: Dangers - Threats - Protection	Environmental Studies - Science - Geography - Skills Labs	Primary Education	Skills labs	Group of teachers
The coastal and marine ecosystem of my place	Environmental Studies - Science (Φυσικά) - Geography - Skills Labs	Primary Education	Environmental Studies - Science (Φυσικά) - Geography - Skills Labs	Group of teachers
Global Warming and Chemical Pollution	Geography, Physics, Chemistry, Skills Lab	Secondary Education & Primary Education	Physics of Lower Secondary School	Individual, Groups of teachers

Discovering the natural wealth of my place: sustainable environmental and mythological routes	Cross-curricularly linked to teaching units of Environmental Studies, History and Language. In the 5th grade, the course of Geography and Social and Political Education is used, and in the 6th grade it is connected with the course of Social and Political Education, Geography and Language.	Primary Education	1st implementation (Language, History, Social and Political Education, Geography, Visual Arts, Informatics and Theater Education) 2nd implementation (Informatics, Arts, Skills Lab)	Individual, Groups of teachers
Urban Planning from the perspective of students	Statistics (Mathematics), History Informatics	Primary Education & Secondary Education	Statistics, History, Informatics, Visual Arts	Individual
I learn about light and use it through photography to capture the problems of my place	Science and Geography	Primary Education	Science and Geography & Visual Arts, Creativity and innovation Clubs	Individual
In a handful of sand...	Biology, Geology Physics Chemistry. As far as Elementary is concerned, Environmental Studies, Science-Geography courses. Arts	Secondary Education & Primary Education	Biology, Geology Physics Chemistry.	Individual
Marine food chain. The big fish eats the small fish	Environmental Studies, Science	Primary Education	Environmental Studies, Science	Individual, Groups of teachers
Machine Learning and Image Recognition in the Service of the Environment	Informatics	Secondary & Primary Education	Informatics	Individual
Blue growth: the macroalgae	Biology, Geography, Chemistry	Lower Secondary School	School activities	Group of teachers
As long as I live I work out...	Physical education, Informatics, Skills Lab, Visual Arts	Primary Education	Physical education, Informatics, Skills Lab, Visual Arts	Group of teachers
Is waste garbage?	Chemistry, Biology	Lower Secondary Education	Chemistry, Biology	Group of teachers
Climate change: past, present and future	Chemistry, Biology, Skills Lab	Lower Secondary Education	Chemistry, Biology	Group of teachers
Humans and Robots	Creative Activities Zone, Projects in Technology, Informatics (Vocational High school)	Vocational School	Creative Activities Zone, Projects in Technology, Informatics (Vocational High school)	Individual

Composting: Together we can do more	Special Educational Needs Schools curriculum	Special Educational Needs Schools	Special Educational Needs Schools curriculum	Group of teachers
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As we can see in Table 1 open schooling in more than 142 schools, 340 teachers and 5390 students in Greece were connected to existing curriculum exploiting (a) each Science subject lesson of Greek curriculum: Science (Φυσικά) and Geography in primary education, Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Geology, Geography in Secondary education, (b) other STEAM subjects lessons such as Informatics, Mathematics, Visual Arts, Language, History, Social and Political Education, Physical education, Theater education and (c) project-based or inquiry-based subject or problem-based compulsory courses such as “Skills Lab” in Primary and Lower Secondary Education, “Environmental studies” in primary education, “Creative activity Zones” and “Project in Technology” in Vocational High School and “Special Educational Needs Curriculum” in Special Educational Needs schools. Also, students and teachers implemented some scenarios in the extracurricular, optional, but recommended by the Ministry, "School Activities" and "Creation and Innovation Club" courses.

In this way, the needs of each type of school were met having teachers working either individually or by groups including interdisciplinary ones (Table 1).

2.3. Topics discussed, activities implemented and students' acceptance

Each year, after the implementation, students were given a questionnaire. Among a lot of questions students were asked:

1. You participated in CONNECT activities in the following topics: select all that apply: (a) Environment, (b) Health, (c) Energy, (d) Climate change, (e) None, (f) Other
2. In which of the following activities have you participated (with your classmates, family or scientists)?: (a) Discussion, (b) Deciding a topic, (c) Asking questions, (d) Voting, (e) Research, (f) Developing a project, (g) Creating recommendations, (h) Presenting results, (i) other.
3. Would you like to participate in new activities such as the ones you have implemented?

After the implementation of the 3rd year, two thousand one (2001) students of all grades from all over Greece have answered:

School Level (Primary and Secondary School):

Figure 1. Students' Year of Studies

The results in Question 1, 2 & 3 are presented below:

Figure 2. Answers to Question 1

Figure 3. Answers to Question 2

Figure 4. Students' acceptance of open schooling

3. Discussion-Conclusions

It is clear that since CONNECT was approved by the Ministry of Education to be implemented in Greek schools as one of the dozens of programs approved each year, teachers jumped at the chance. Did they have the opportunity to do multiple programs at once? All these three (3) years we have had the opportunity to create a community by meeting synchronously with Zoom and phone calls with the teachers and asynchronously through the platform and emails [10]. 90% of the teachers had answered the previous question that they did not have time to do more than one program and that was CONNECT.

1. But why did they choose CONNECT among all these approved programs, and above all how did they manage to implement it to the end?
2. Why did we have participation and success even from the 12th grade, that is, from the grade in which the children take the Panhellenic exams for admission to universities (Figure 1), whereas in other countries in CONNECT that was not the case [4]?

We claim that the answer is based on the data of the previous section:

First, each teacher was given the opportunity to meet their needs, including curriculum requirements, either by using a ready-made scenario that they adapted or by creating their own. But how? Because they were given theory-based principles and design guidelines and also the opportunity to be coached by curriculum experts who were giving them feedback. In this way, every relevant subject of the Greek curriculum was taken advantage of, as well as the optional extracurricular activities.

Second, in more than half of the cases (Table 1), teachers worked together to implement cross-curricular educational scenarios taking advantage of project-based/inquiry-based subject /problem-based compulsory courses and optional extracurricular courses. The latter case agrees with the recommendations of Mulero et al. [3] on sustainable open schooling, about interdisciplinary groups of teachers especially if the curriculum is strict.

Third, technology helped for (a) coaching and co-creation of resources (b) collaboration among teachers and also (c) bringing 82 experts and other stakeholders “close” to students through teleconferences.

It also needed both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation [11, 2]. Teachers were intrinsically motivated by seeing their students owning the learning process by discussing, doing projects, presenting results at the CONNECT Student Conference (<https://connect.pdekritis.gr/studentconference2023/>) and other forums, by deciding topics etc. (Figure 3). They were also intrinsically motivated by sharing their work with other colleagues. They were also extrinsically motivated because they were acknowledged through certificates and credits they have received for their authoring work.

But how was open schooling implemented in this context? Was it inquiry-based as Bogner & Sotiriou [11] and Okada et al. [4] suggest for Open Science Schooling? How were the topics selected? Our data (Figure 3) shows that for students it was a project-based approach. The topic was most often predetermined by the teacher (Table 1), but half of the time, left the students with the opportunity to guide the procedure of learning by choosing the subtopics. We assume that this was to ensure that it fit the curriculum. Students' perceptions about the kind of activity they have participated in can be explained because inquiry-based, project-based and problem-based learning share the same theory of constructivism [12].

Was it Open Schooling in Science Education what we have done? Our scenario design guidelines and the data show (Table 1, Figure 2) that although the topics were aimed at the 17 goals of sustainable development, students perceived that it was mostly about the environment or climate change. I guess this is not bizarre if we hypothesize that by adopting "open schooling for sustainability" we are transferred from "Science Education" to "Science education for sustainability" where the notion of Environment has a more generic meaning.

Therefore, we could conclude that the implementation of the open schooling in Greece through the CONNECT project was rather a successful in terms of student's acceptance (Figure 4), large-scale, bottom-up endeavour supported by curriculum experts and legitimized by the Ministry [2], which was adapted, strengthened and limited by the Greek context.

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